

Research Article

Smart Xcess@BCW

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Abstract: In this digital era, students face various challenges in adapting to modern learning methods, especially new students who often experience difficulties such as a lack of relevant reference materials, difficulty adapting to new learning approaches, and the burden of the cost of purchasing physical textbooks. Digital technology has emerged as a solution to this issue, with the use of Smart Xcess@BCW becoming one of the increasingly popular approaches in improving learning effectiveness. Smart Xcess@BCW offer the advantage of providing interactive, dynamic, and easily accessible content that can adapt to the needs of a new generation of students who are more inclined to technology. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the use of digital learning Smart Xcess@BCW in the Building Construction Workshop course compared to three similar courses using conventional method (Brickwork & Concrete Workshop, Plumbing & Carpentry Workshop, IBS Workshop). This study involves a quantitative approach through analysis of final exam results to see the impact of using Smart Xcess@BCW on students' understanding, academic achievement, and their motivation. The findings of the study show that the use of Smart Xcess@BCW significantly increases students' understanding of the concepts taught, strengthens self-learning, and has a positive impact on academic achievement. The data reveals that Smart Xcess@BCW supported learning in the Building Construction Workshop outperforms the traditional methods, particularly in producing a higher proportion of top-performing students ('A' grades). In addition, the use of Smart Xcess@BCW also successfully increases student motivation by increasing focus and enthusiasm in learning. Overall, this study suggests that the integration of Smart Xcess@BCW as a learning tool can enrich educational experience and provide guidance to higher education institutions in adapting a more effective digital learning approach for today's generation of students.

Keywords: Smart Xcess@BCW; Digital Learning; Learning Effectiveness.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Smart Xcess@BCW is a production of innovation in the form of interactive learning in practical T&L developed for the Building Construction Workshop course. The development of this innovation has been made in the English version to meet the needs of the curriculum in learning and teaching at the Polytechnic. The production of Smart Xcess@BCW aims to facilitate the teaching and learning process in practical work while increasing student interest. The development of this interactive learning innovation is also in line with the development of technology in today's education which requires more creative, innovative and interactive teaching techniques (Surachman et al., 2024). The use of interactive materials can make learning easier and more interesting (Omar, 2022).

Figure 1. Smart Xcess@BCW front view

1.1 Purpose

Issues and challenges in understanding civil engineering practical procedures among students are an important topic in the context of TVET education in higher education institutions. Learning practical procedures involves an understanding of techniques, technology, and safety related to the field of civil engineering (Ealangov, 2023). However, there are several main challenges that prevent students from gaining a deep understanding, among them the problem of lack of practical exposure, weakness in theoretical knowledge, lack of suitable facilities, time constraints, and the attitude and motivation of the students themselves (Bahtiar et al., 2020). The objective of this innovation are as follows:

- a. Provide learning resources that can be accessed digitally anytime and anywhere to facilitate students acquisition of knowledge about civil engineering practice without the constraints of location and time.
- b. Help students understand and master the steps and practical engineering procedures through clear explanations and the use of multimedia elements such as videos and interactive simulations.
- c. Foster active learning by providing interactive activities and quiz questions that can stimulate critical thinking and enhance collaboration between students and instructors through technology-based features.
- d. Applying the use of modern technology in the practical learning process is in line with the needs of an increasingly digital and high-tech industry.
- e. Encourage students to learn autonomously with features such as digital notes, step-by-step practice guides, and concept explanations that facilitate self-understanding.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Figure 2. Innovation planning and timeline

Based on Figure 2, the development of this innovation has been divided into 3 phases which is First Phase: Design Smart Notes@BCW, Second Phase: Design Smart Handbook@BCW and Third Phase: Design Smart Xcess@BCW with duration around 4 months.

2.1 First Phase: Design Smart Notes@BCW

The first phase of the development of this innovation focuses on the preparation of notes, practical worksheets, videos, and 3D images related to practical work. There are two parts developed, as listed below:

- a. Part 1 : Overview of Building Construction Workshop
- b. Part 2 : Construction Workshop
 - Part 2(i) : Concrete Laboratory
 - Part 2(ii) : Carpentry Workshop
 - Part 2(iii) : Plumbing Workshop
 - Part 2(iv) : Brickwork Workshop
 - Part 2(v) : IBS Workshop

As the final stage of this phase, an eBook was created and published (https://anyflip.com/qrklq/exwy/#google_vignette). For an intriguing presentation of this eBook, we utilized Canva for the appearance and Revit Software for the 3D image. This eBook focusing on Visual Learning Style users.

Figure 3. Smart Notes@BCW front view

2.2 Second Phase: Design Smart Handbook@BCW

To condense the eBook's content, a handbook of no longer than ten pages was designed, complete with a barcode for notes, practical worksheets, videos, and 3D images. This image helps users focus on the subject to be attained, whether it is notes for a specific topic, a practical worksheet, a movie, or a 3D images. This handbook was printed as a booklet in A5 size, focusing on Auditory Learning Style users.

Figure 4. Smart Handbook@BCW view

2.3 Third Phase: Design Smart Xcess@BCW

The development of Smart Xcess@BCW for the Building Construction Workshop course focuses on the 5 elements as follows:

- a. Interactive and Dynamic Learning: Smart Xcess@BCW enables the delivery of more interactive information with multimedia elements such as video, animation, and simulation. This can help users understand the concept of public construction more deeply and simplify the complex practical learning process.

- b. **Accessibility and Flexibility:** Users can access Smart Xcess@BCW anytime and anywhere through digital devices. This makes it easier for users to review and carry out learning activities outside of the physical classroom, increasing the flexibility of learning.
- c. **Reduction in the Cost of Printed Materials:** The use of Smart Xcess@BCW reduces the need for printed materials such as textbooks and practical notes. This not only saves costs for users and institutions but also helps in environmental preservation efforts by reducing the use of paper.
- d. **Student-Centred Learning:** Smart Xcess@BCW can be adapted to support a variety of learning styles, including visual, auditory, and kinesthetics. Features such as interactive quizzes and practice sheets in the eBook allow students to test their own understanding, promoting more effective and student-centred learning.
- e. **Technology Integration in Education:** Smart Xcess@BCW utilizes digital and multimedia technology, in line with modern digital learning trends, as well as increasing users' level of readiness for the use of technology in the field of civil engineering.

Based on the elements above, Smart Xcess@BCW was developed using Glideapps to fulfil the target. This Smart Xcess@BCW was developed with integrated four main elements: interactive, self-access, unlimited time and place, also fun learning. Users can download the apps using a link or barcode and store them on their devices. They can access notes, practical worksheets, videos, and 3D images through their digital devices at anytime and anywhere. Besides that, users can also enjoy the games created and enhance their knowledge at the same time. Users can download Smart Xcess@BCW using the barcode below or link <https://go.glideapps.com/play/scwnssgokwh3mv0oltzh>.

Figure 5. Smart Xcess@BCW barcode

3. FINDINGS

Figure 6. Results for similar courses before and after using Smart Xcess@BCW

The bar chart in Figure 6 compares the final examination results of students in four workshop-based courses, highlighting the performance differences between those taught using conventional methods (Brickwork & Concrete Workshop, Plumbing & Carpentry Workshop, IBS Workshop) and Building Construction Workshop, which employs Smart Xcess@BCW digital learning. The Building Construction Workshop demonstrates a significant edge, with 97% of students achieving an 'A' grade and 3% obtaining a 'B.' Notably, no students scored below 'B,' indicating the effectiveness of Smart Xcess@BCW in achieving high academic performance. In contrast, courses using conventional teaching methods show relatively lower performance. The Brickwork & Concrete Workshop had 70% of students scoring 'A,' and 30% achieving a 'B,' with no lower grades. Plumbing & Carpentry Workshop had 76% scoring 'A' and 24% 'B,' while the IBS Workshop achieved slightly better results with 88% 'A' grades and 12% 'B.' The data reveals that Smart Xcess@BCW supported learning in the Building Construction Workshop outperforms the traditional methods, particularly in producing a higher proportion of top-performing students ('A' grades). This highlights the potential for digital tools like Smart XCESS to enhance engagement, understanding, and performance compared to traditional teaching approaches. The absence of lower grades (C, D, E, F) across all courses suggests a baseline competency among students, but the digital learning methodology clearly drives superior outcomes.

4. DISCUSSION

The benefits and features of Smart Xcess@BCW include:

- a) Interactive Augmented Reality (AR) Experience:
 - i. Cognitive Development: Students can gain a clear understanding of building construction workshop and their fundamentals.
 - ii. Psychomotor Skills: Students can interpret lab sheet procedure and visualize the output of building construction process and components.
 - iii. Affective Attitude: Students can foster creativity and embrace diversity in the learning process.
- b) Accessible Anywhere, Anytime:
 - i. Smart Xcess@BCW can be accessed conveniently, whether during online or offline classes, allowing students to learn at their own pace.
- c) Cost-Effective Solution:
 - i. The implementation of Smart Xcess@BCW offers a cost-effective alternative to traditional teaching methods, eliminating the need for physical models or extensive resources.
- d) Broad Knowledge Solution:
 - i. Educators, polytechnic students, and higher institution students, particularly those studying in civil engineering, can benefit from Smart Xcess@BCW's augmented reality representation of building construction process.
 - ii. Smart Xcess@BCW can be adapted for technical courses offered in educational institutions, such as construction management and engineering.
 - iii. Construction industry stakeholders, including clients, consultants, contractors, and regulatory bodies like CIDB, JKR, PAM, IEM, RISM, and BQSM, can also leverage Smart Xcess@BCW for their needs.

5. CONCLUSION

The development of Smart Xcess@BCW as an augmented reality (AR) digital learning material presents a significant advancement in teaching and learning practices, especially in comparison to traditional reliance on two-dimensional (2D) drawings. With this AR application, students can easily visualize and understand the various components of building construction. Moreover, Smart Xcess@BCW is suitable for both physical face-to-face and online learning modes. Furthermore, the integration of augmented reality (AR) elements in the learning and teaching process aligns with the principles of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0), promoting innovative and technologically advanced approaches to education.

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